

NOTES

Studies on Optically Active Alkylated Derivatives of Strychnine and Brucine

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The alkylation of strychnine and brucine at N_a and N_b was studied by J. Tafel^{1,2,3}, Perkin and Robinson⁴ and Mitsuwa and workers⁵. The alkylation at active methylene carbon was undertaken to prepare the optically active alkylated derivatives of strychnine and brucine, by alkyl halides in presence of sodium ethoxide in absolute ethanol as follows :

where $x = H$ strychnine

$x = OCH_3$ brucine

R = Alkyl groups from $-CH_3$, $-C_2H_5I$, $-C_3H_7Br$, $-C_4H_9Br$ and $-C_5H_{11}Br$.

EXPERIMENTAL

The alkaloid strychnine or brucine (0.01M) was taken in absolute ethanol and sodium ethoxide (0.01M) in ethanol was added with stirring and warming to 40°–50° for half an hour. Alkyl halide (0.02M) was added to the cool reaction mixture and refluxed for 2 to 4 hrs on a water bath. The hot mixture was poured into HCl (5%) maintaining temperature at 50°–60°. The acidic solution was neutralised by ammonia and kept overnight. The alkyl derivative separated which was filtered, washed with ether and recrystallised from alcohol.

1. J. Tafel *Ann.*, 1891, **24**, 264.
2. J. Tafel, *Ber.*, 1890, **23**, 2731.
3. J. Tafel *et al.*, *Ann.*, 1899, **33**, 304.
4. Perkin and Robinson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 767.
5. M. Kotake and Mitsuwa. *Chem. abs.*, 1934, **28** 5460.

TABLE 1
Strychnine Compounds of the type:

R from	Yield %	M.P. °C	Sp. rotation in chloroform (<i>l</i> = 1)
Methyl iodide	47.7	263	-131.0
Ethyl iodide	48.5	262	-128.7
Propyl bromide	39.8	260	-130.9
<i>n</i> -Butyl bromide	41.5	248	-125.7
iso-amyl bromide	36.5	258	-127.0

TABLE 2
Brucine Compounds of the type:

R from	Yield %	M.P. °C	Sp. Rotation in Chloroform (<i>l</i> = 1)
Methyl iodide	49.0	105	-103.5
Ethyl iodide	43.0	109	-103.1
Propyl bromide	39.2	107	- 97.0
Butyl bromide	45.5	127	- 91.0
iso-amyl bromide	39.8	121	- 94.5

All the compounds described above gave correct C, H, analysis.

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